

**Firm-Level Corporate Governance and Firm Value of Deposit
Money Banks Listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group**

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Abstract

The study examines corporate governance and firm value of Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange during the period 2012 to 2021. Although the relationship between firm value and corporate governance has been examined, however, it remains unclear as to whether this relationship is causal, i.e. the whether the relationship is bidirectional, specifically from an emerging economy such as Nigeria. The study used longitudinal research design, taking a census of the entire thirteen (13) DMBs during the period 2012 to 2021, secondary data sourced from the audited annual reports of the samples banks. Both the 2 Stage Least Square (2SLS) and the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) were adopted. Giving that the GMM estimates failed the AR (2) test which is a fundamental requirement for its reliability, the study based its inferences on the estimates from the 2SLS technique. The result revealed that both corporate governance and firm value are causal. On specific components of corporate governance, board independence, board size, managerial, institutional and foreign ownership had significant impact on firm value at 5% while board financial expertise had insignificant impact. Based on the findings, the study concludes that corporate governance impact firm value vice versa. Therefore, the study recommends that firms should actively improve their governance practices in order to achieve higher valuation.

1. Introduction

The market value of a firm, reflected through the stock market price is an important concept for investors because it shows how well the market perceives the company.

The stock market price reflects the potentials of the company in the future or the overall investor's assessment of its own capital owned by a particular company. This suggests that a high share price indicates shareholders' prosperity vice versa (Ngatemin et al., 2018). Several studies have been done on the empirical causal link between firm-level corporate governance and firm value (Ahmad & Sallau, 2018; Oladeji & Agbesanya, 2019; Urbi & Maximiliano, 2019). An investigation of the prior literature presents interesting methodological issues for discourse. First, despite the emergence of a growing body of literature demonstrating the correlation between firm-level governance and firm valuation, it remains unclear as to whether this relationship is causal, i.e. the whether the relationship is bidirectional. For instance, Demsetz and Lehn (1985) opine that firms may endogenously select different governance practices; therefore, firms may actually play dual roles both passive and active in their governance practices. Not only are firm value affected by governance practices, but they will also actively improve their governance practices to achieve higher valuation (Bhagat & Bolton, 2008).

Therefore, the premise in prior literature that the influence of governance on firm value is exogenous may have led to inconsistent results. Again, there is a particular line of thought that the current actions of a firm affects future corporate governance as well as performance, which will in turn affect the firms' future actions (Hermalin & Weisbach, 2004; Wintoki et al., 2008), therefore there may be suspicion of endogeneity problem. Also, Coles et al. (2006) opine that in order to alleviate the problem of slowly moving corporate governance indices over time, there is the need to account for the suspicion of endogeneity which has become a crucial issue in investigating the effects of corporate governance on firm value, an issue which has been largely ignored in prior literature unlike a hand few of studies that have examined such endogeneity problem (Ammann et al., 2009; Chen et al., 2010). Therefore, the findings of prior studies cannot be relied on because: (i) most of the studies assumed that corporate governance is exogenously determined viz-a-viz firm value and this could be misleading; (ii) the suspected endogeneity issue in corporate governance and firm value relationship which most prior studies ignored may have also lead to bias estimation; and (iii) corporate governance and firm value studies in emerging economies such as Nigeria have not been sufficiently addressed, with particular reference to the methodological issues raised in the foregoing. Therefore, the aim of this study is to examine firm-level corporate governance and firm value of deposit money banks listed in the Nigerian Exchange Group.

2.2 Conceptual Definitions

2.2-1 Firm Value

The value of the firm is the market value of debt and equity securities of companies outstanding (Keown, 2004). According to Agus and Sartono (2001), a firm's value is the sales value of a firm that is operating. Weston and Copeland (2002) defines a firm's value as the fair value of firm that describe investors' perception of the issuers concerned. High stock prices make the firm's value is also high, and enhance market confidence not only to the firm's current performance but also on the firm's prospects for the future. Corporate value is an economic measure which reflects the market value of a business (Nguyen & Bui, 2018). Hermuningsih (2013) posits that firm value is crucial since it can be a sign of company's performance and one of the main factors influencing in investor perception of the company. Corporate value is an important concept for investors, as it is an important indicator of how the market perceives the company as a whole. Several surrogates such as Tobin's Q and share prices have been used to reflect the market value of firms.

2.2-2 Board of Directors

According to the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance (NCCG) issued by the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria ([FRCN], 2018, p.1), it states that "a successful company is headed by an effective Board which is responsible for providing entrepreneurial and strategic leadership as well as promoting ethical culture and responsible citizens. As a link between stakeholders and the company, the Board is to exercise oversight and control to ensure that management acts in the best interest of shareholders and other stakeholders while sustaining the prosperity of the company". This study proceed to discuss some of these board attribute.

2.2-3 Board Independence

This refers to the ratio of independent outside directors to the total number of directors on the board. Outside directors are non-executive directors of either affiliate or independent in nature (Dalton et al., 1999). The affiliate directors are those who have business ties with the firm and this tends to undermine objective participation in board decision making. The independent directors are those directors who do not have direct or indirect relationship with the firm or its affiliate, therefore can objectively participate in the board. The NCCG issued by FRCN (2018, p.7) states that "an independent non-executive director should represent a strong independent voice on the board, be independent in character and judgment and

accordingly be free from such relationships or circumstances with the company, its management, or substantial shareholders as may, or appear to, impair his ability to make an independent judgment". Again, the independent non-executive director is a non-executive director who does not possess a shareholding in the company the value of which is material to the holder such as will impair his independence or in excess of 0.01% of the paid up capital of the company. Non-executive directors bring to bear their knowledge, expertise and independent judgment on issues of strategy and performance on the board. Independent non-executive directors bring a high degree of objectivity to the board for sustaining stakeholder trust and confidence. On the other hand, the executive directors support the Managing Director/Chief Executive Officer in the operations and management of the company. According to the NCCG issued by (2018), there should be an appropriate mix between the executive, non-executive and independent non-executive directors on the board. Preferably, that most of the non-executive directors should be independent.

2.2-4 Board Size

This refers to the number of directors on the board. Board size seems to differ from one country to another. There are often two schools of thought in this regard: (i) small; and (ii) large board size. The NCCG by FRCN (2018) did not give a specific number of directors on the board. Rather, it states that the board should be of sufficient size to effectively undertake and fulfil its business; to oversee, monitor, direct and control the company's activities and be relative to the scale and complexity of its operation. It also states that the board should consider the following factors in determining the requisite number of its members are: (i) appropriate mix of knowledge, skills and experience, including the business, commercial and industry experience needed to govern the company; (ii) appropriate mix of executive, non-executive and independent non-executive members such that majority of the board are non-executive directors. It is desirable that most of the non-executive directors are independent; (iii) need for a sufficient number of members that qualify to serve on the committees of the board; (iv) need to secure quorum at meeting; and (v) diversity targets relating to the composition of the board. Conger and Lawler (1998) opined that there is no ideal size for a board, rather the right size should be driven by how effective the board is able to operate as a team. In the same vein, Park and Shin (2004) opined that the right size should be a function of how well it will impact on the board performance. Prior researchers argued that large board of director is more diversified in terms of directors' background, expertise and resources (Dalton et al., 1999; Haniffa & Hudaib, 2006).

However, large board is seen to be ineffective in decision making, has higher managerial cost, poor corporate governance and easier for CEOs to control (Al-Manaser et al., 2012). On small board size, Hermalin and Weisbach (2001) stated that a smaller board size offers a better monitoring on management. Prior studies have suggested that a company's performance is better when the board size is smaller (Andres et al., 2005). On the contrary, small board size is characterized with absence of diversity such as expertise, nationality, external linkages etc. which could undermine firm output.

2.2-5 Board Financial Expertise

Financial expertise implies being a financial expert as a result of past employment experience in finance or accounting, requisite professional certification in accounting, or any other comparable experience or background which resulted in the individuals sophistication, including being or having being a CEO or other senior officer with financial oversight responsibility in a particular organization (Blue Ribbon Committee ([BRC], 1999). The NCCG by FRCN (2018) opined that that the board of directors should promote diversity in its membership across a variety of attributes relevant for promoting better decision-making and effective governance. One of such attributes as stipulated in the code is field of knowledge. Abernathy et al. (2014) classified financial expertise into three groups: (i) accounting expertise; (ii) non-accounting expertise; and (iii) non-financial expertise. Aifuwa and Embele (2018) opined that to become an expert in a board, a director must possess adequate educational and professional experience in areas of finance, accounting and auditing. It is important for board members to have an understanding of accounting principles and financial statements which will lead to better board oversight.

2.3 Ownership Structure

NCCG issued by FRCN (2018, p.29) stated that board of directors should encourage institutional investors to "positively influence the standard of corporate governance and promote value creation in the companies in which they invest, monitor conformance with the provision of the code and raise concerns as appropriate". This implies that the NCCG recognizes the role different ownership structure could play in organization output. Therefore, shareholders engagement in enforcing corporate governance practice is paramount. Giving the importance of the board of directors and shareholders engagement in fostering corporate governance, the attributes of the board and nature of shareholding could have specific implications on

organization output, in this case firm value. Ownership structure falls within two broad classification: (i) concentrated versus dispersed; and (ii) types of ownership structure such as institutional, foreign, managerial etc. This study proceed to discuss some of these ownership structure.

2.3-1 Managerial Ownership

Managerial ownership, also known as directors' ownership is the accumulated shares owned by Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) which include restricted shares but not included stock options (Zhou, 2011). According to Salehi and Baezgar (2011), managerial ownership is the percentage of shares held by officers and directors. It can also be defined as manager who has the power to take and make decision about the company strategies and policies (Chen & Yu, 2012). The effect of managerial ownership on organizational output has been appraised from two perspectives: (i) alignment of interest hypothesis; and (ii) entrenchment hypothesis. According to the alignment of interest hypothesis, increase in managerial ownership forces managers to take the responsibility of wealth, consequence and thus coordinates the interest of management and shareholders. This reduces managerial incentives to consume perquisites and expropriate shareholders wealth (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). According to Brickley et al. (1998), director equity ownership is an incentive to enable them monitor managers effectively. On the other hand, managerial entrenchment effect hypothesis as enunciated by posits that managers with larger ownership have greater control over firms, and therefore possess more freedom to act in their own private interest, often to the detriment of those shareholders who engage in opportunistic behavior to serve their own interest, since they are less likely to be controlled and dismissed (Morck et al., 1988).

2.3-2 Institutional Ownership

These are shareholdings by corporate institutions such as banks, insurance companies, retirement or pension funds, hedges funds, investment advisors and mutual funds. NCCG by FRCN (2018, p. 29) opined that the board should encourage institutional investors to: (i) "positively influence the standard of corporate governance and promote value creation in the companies in which they invest; and (ii). Also, the institutional investors should monitor conformance with the provision of the code and raise concerns as appropriate". According to Gillan and Starks (2003), corporate monitoring by institutional investors can constrain managers' behaviors because they have the opportunity, resources, and ability to monitor, discipline, and influence managers. Also, Balsam et al (2003) argued that the institutional shareholdings has the advantage of discovering earning management

practices. However, they can use their position to the detriment of other smaller shareholders.

2.3-3 Foreign Ownership

According to the Organization of Economic Community and Development ([OECD], 1990, foreign ownership refers shareholdings by nationals outside the country of origin in local firms. An (2015) posits that higher ratios of foreign ownership induces companies to improve their transparency and to reduce opportunistic managerial accounting choices and decisions. They have better incentives and expertise to independently observe companies. Foreign ownership can effectively monitor management by increasing pressure on managers to release timely corporate reports.

2.4 Empirical Review of Literature

The study of Dung (2011) investigates the relation between corporate governance and firm value by using information taken from of Vietnamese Listed Companies on Ho Chi Minh Stock Exchange (HOSE) and Ha Noi Stock Exchange (HNX) at the year-end 2009. The findings show that the dual position of CEO and Chairman has a positive relation with firm value. Besides, age of director and the number of directors meeting play important roles in firm value. However, no significant impact of board size, board gender diversity, top ten shareholders concentration and levels of state ownership on firm value. The regression model of market performance shows that the duality of CEO and Chairman and the number of independent directors are significant impact on firm value. Garcí'a and Sa'nchez (2011) examine the effects of various dimensions of the Spanish ownership structure on firm value. The various dimension of ownership structure used were ownership concentration, insider ownership and bank ownership while firms' value was proxy by Tobin's Q. The results show that ownership concentration exhibits a positive relationship with firm value. The findings suggest that ownership concentration appears to influence firm value favorably, however at a high level of concentrate ownership structure, the firm vale tends to decline. These findings, which are different from the result of other studies, can be explained by the differences in corporate governance systems. Bruno and Claessens (2010) use data from Risk Metrics (formerly Institutional Shareholder Services (ISS)) and find that firm value depends on both country-level shareholder protection laws and firm-level corporate governance attributes. In addition, these relations are more pronounced in companies that depend on external financing. Aggarwal et al. (2009) also use ISS data and compare the governance of non-U.S. firms with a matched set of U.S. firms

and find that the valuation of non-U.S. firms falls as their governance index value decreases as compared to the governance index of matching U.S. firms.

Chhaochharia and Laeven (2009) also using the ISS database, distinguish between governance attributes that are legally required and attributes that are adopted voluntarily. They show that firms that voluntarily adopt a more rigorous corporate governance structure are rewarded with a higher firm value. Sulong and Nor (2010) examine the effect of governance mechanisms on firm value. Their research utilizes a panel data analysis of 403 firms listed on the Bursa Malaysia over a four-year period from years 2002 to 2005. The data is analyzed using the generalized least square (GLS) estimation technique. The results highlight the importance of moderating role played by board governance variables with types of ownership structure to influence firm value. However, the benefits of better corporate governance through enhanced board governance are not the same across all firms since their incentives vary with respect to dividend and different types of ownership structure mechanisms. The study of Feng-Li & Lin (2010) examines the relationship between institutional ownership and firm value. They examined 221 listed Taiwanese companies during the period 1997 to 2006. The study adopts an advanced panel threshold regression model to test whether there is an “optimal” institutional ownership, which causes threshold effects and asymmetrical relationships between institutional ownership and firm value. Tobin's Q is used as a proxy for firm value. The findings show that there is a threshold effect between institutional ownership and firm value at 81.2%. When the institutional ownership is less than 81.2%, there is no relationship between institutional ownership and Tobin's Q. When the institutional ownership is greater than 81.2%, the Tobin's Q increases by 1.25%, with a 1% increase in the institutional ownership. These results are consistent with the effective monitoring hypotheses when the institutional ownership greater than 81.2% at which point the firm's value will start to increase. Similarly, Gompers et al. (2003) found that firms that have strong shareholders' rights have higher firm value, higher profits, and higher sales growth.

Hermalin and Weisbach (1991) and Bhagat and Black (2002) also found no link between the proportion of independent directors and value of the firm as measured by Tobin's Q. Thus, the evidence relating to board independence and firm value varies. However, Yermack (1996) and Brown and Caylor (2004) found that the separation of a CEO and Chairman's position in a company makes a firm more valuable. Rahayu and Rashidah (2005) confirm that concentrated ownership has a tendency to increase firm value. The result from their study implies that

concentrated ownership coincides with a lack of investor protection because shareholders who are not protected from controllers will seek to protect themselves by becoming controllers. Hence, the important implication of the significantly positively related between concentrated ownership and firm value is that large shareholders/investors have an incentive to monitor management and solve the free-rider problem. Aggarwal and Williamson (2006) and Brown and Caylor (2006) use the ISS database to construct governance indices for U.S. firms only and both find a positive relation between corporate governance and firm value. McConnell and Servaes (1990) examines the relationship between institutional ownership and firm value. Using a sample of 1173 firms listed on NYSE/AMEX in 1976 and another 1093 firms in 1986, the study found a positive relationship between institutional ownership and firm value. Studies by Hermalin and Weisbach, 1991 and Bhagat and Black (2002) found no relationship between the proportion of outside directors and Tobin's Q. Yermack (1996) found an inverse relation between board size and Tobin's Q. The study by Callahan et al. (2003) found a positive relationship between management participation in the director selection process and Tobin's Q. Gompers et al. (2003) used Investor Responsibility Research Center (IRRC) data. Gompers, et al, classified 24 governance factors into five groups (tactics for delaying hostile takeover, voting rights, director/officer protection, other takeover defenses, and state laws). They created a G-Index by summing 24 binary governance factors. This G-Index has been used in studies to represent governance even though it is more reflective of an anti-takeover protection index, rather than a corporate governance index (Cremers & Nair, 2005). They found that firms with fewer shareholder rights have lower firm valuations and lower stock returns. The study of Bebchuk and Cohen (2005) shows that staggered boards have a negative impact on the value of the firm. Bebchuk and Cohen (2005) show that a six-factor firm entrenchment index fully drives the relation between G-Index and firm value. Cremers and Nair (2005) show that a three-factor external governance index impedes firm valuation. Cremers and Nair (2005) argue that effective corporate governance requires both internal and external measures such as shareholder activism. Brown and Caylor (2005) examine the links between corporate governance and firm valuation, using a far more extensive database than the IRRC database. They create simple summary governance index using 51 ISS data items. Similar to Gompers, et al (2003), they show that their new Gov.-Score increases in firm value. They also show that a small subset of factors fully drives the relation between ISS corporate governance data and firm value.

2.5 Theoretical Review

Various theories exist within the corporate governance context. Sanda et al. (2005) and Ranti (2011) identified the agency theory, the stewardship theory and the stakeholder theory as the three prominent theories of corporate governance. However, for the purpose of this study is anchored on the agency theory. According to the Agency as presented by Berle and Means (1932), however popularized Jensen and Meckling (1976), due to the separation between ownership and control, agency problems occur when the interests of agents are different from those of principals. The principals are the shareholders while the agents are the managers. Depending on the parties involved in conflicts, agency problems can be categorized into four: managerial agency (between stockholders and management), debt agency (between stockholders and bondholders), social agency (between private and public sectors); and political agency (between agents of the public sector and the rest of society or taxpayers). However, this study focuses on the agency-principal problems (between managers and stockholders). Jensen and Meckling (1976) posit that shareholders are the residual claimants after other parties; their rights are the weakest. Corporate governance is therefore made to protect and promote the interests of shareholders. In order to resolve the conflicting interest between shareholders and managers, corporate governance, a system by which an entity is directed and control is put in place. One of the benefits of corporate governance is that it helps to increase future cash flows and also reduces a firm's weighted average cost of capital (WACC), therefore agency theory suggests a positive relationship between good corporate governance and firm value. Corporate governance is classified into: (i) internal; and (ii) external governance mechanisms. The internal mechanisms are the boards of directors which monitors management operations and processes while the external mechanisms include ownership structure, protection of minority shareholders, legal infrastructure, and market for corporate control (Gillan, 2006). For the purpose of this study, board attributes (board independence, board size and board financial expertise) and ownership structure (managerial, institutional and foreign ownership) are examined as key corporate governance attributes that could impact firm value.

3 Methodology

The study adopts a longitudinal research design. The population consist of the entire firms listed in the banking sector in the respective Stock Exchange as at 31st December, 2021. In the NSE, we had thirteen (13) banks listed. The choice of the banking sector is that they are strictly regulated and their compliance level seems

high to regulatory framework. Also, their annual reports are more detailed compared to other sectors and the variables of interest are adequately disclosed in their annual reports. Due to the finite and small size of the banks listed in the respective Stock Exchange, the study took a census of the population as its sample size. Secondary data is used for this study. The data is sourced from the audited annual reports of listed banks in the respective Stock Exchange during the period 2012-2021 financial year. The researcher utilizes only corporate annual reports because they are readily available, accessible and also provide a greater potential for comparability of results.

The data analyses methods are: (i) two stage least square (2SLS); and (ii) system Generalized Methods of Moment (GMM). The choice of the 2SLS is due to the two-way association between the dependent and independent variables i.e. firm value and corporate governance. Therefore, it is not advisable to use a single equation model for the description of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. The function should not be treated as a single equation model, rather as a wider system of equations which can effectively describe the relationships among all variables. The choice of the GMM is due to the suspicion of endogeneity, a situation in which an explanatory variable is correlated with the error term. According to Campos and Kinoshita (2003), the GMM estimation method is used to address the biases due to unobserved cross-country effect, the presence of lagged dependent variables, and the problem of endogeneity. The system GMM is suitable for the study because it provides a consistent parameter estimates by utilizing instruments that can be obtained from the orthogonality conditions that exist between the lagged values of a variable and the disturbance term. In this case, neither the fixed effect estimation, nor Generalized Least Square (GLS) estimation technique will produce a reliable estimates. Other tests that were carried out in the dynamic model are the J-statistics/sargan and arrelano and bond.

Theoretical Framework and Model Specification

The study is anchored on agency theory. The agency theory has its origin in the Berlie and Means (1932) doctrine of separation of ownership from control. Therefore, owners of business put in place board of directors that serves as a link between stakeholders and the Company, and to exercise oversight and control to ensure that management acts in the best interest of the shareholders and other stakeholders while sustaining the prosperity of the Company (FRCN, 2018). Again, study adapts the model of Chen et al. (2018). The study of Chen et al. (2018) addresses two the fundamental methodological issues raised in this

study: (i) assumption that corporate governance is exogenously determined which is misleading; and (ii) the endogeneity problem associated with firm-level corporate governance and firm value. The model form this study is an adaption of the model of Chen et al. (2018).

The functional form of the model is stated thus:

$$FV = f(BND, BS, BFEXP, MOWN, INSOWN, FOWN, CGS, FS, FA, FL) \text{-----(i)}$$

Where: FV= firm value; BND= board independence; BS= board size; BFEXP= board financial expertise; CGS= corporate governance score; MOWN= managerial ownership; INSOWN= institutional ownership; FOWN= foreign ownership; FS= firm size; FA= firm age; and FL= firm leverage.

The econometric form is stated thus:

$$FV_{it} = \emptyset_0 + \emptyset_1 BND_{it} + \emptyset_2 BS_{it} + \emptyset_3 BFEXP_{it} + \emptyset_4 MOWN_{it} + \emptyset_5 INSOWN_{it} + \emptyset_6 FOWN_{it} + \emptyset_7 CGS_{it} + \emptyset_8 FS_{it} + \emptyset_9 FA_{it} + \emptyset_{10} FL_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{-----(ii)}$$

Where: i= cross sections; t= time; \emptyset_0 = intercept; $\emptyset_1 - \emptyset_{10}$ = unknown coefficients; ε = error term.

The functional form of the model is stated thus:

$$CGS = f(FV, FS, FA, FL) \text{-----(iii)}$$

The econometric form is stated thus:

$$CGS_{it} = \emptyset_0 + \emptyset_1 FV_{it} + \emptyset_2 FS_{it} + \emptyset_3 FA_{it} + \emptyset_4 FL_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \text{-----(vi)}$$

Variable measurement

1. **Firm value:** measured using share price (Nguyen & Bui, 2018).
2. **Board independence:** measured with the ratio of independent non-executive directors to total number of directors in the board (Kuan & Chu, 2011).
3. **Board size:** measured with the number of directors in the board (Kuan & Chu, 2011).
4. **Board financial expertise:** measured with the ratio of directors with financial education/experience background to the total number of directors in the board (Baatwah et al., 2015).
5. **Managerial equity ownership:** measured with the percentage of equity holdings by CEO and board of directors' members to total equity holdings of the company (Ozkan & Ozkan, 2004).
6. **Institutional ownership:** measured with the percentage of equity holdings by corporate investors to total equity holdings of the company (Chung & Zhang, 2014).
7. **Foreign ownership:** measured with the percentage of equity holdings by foreign shareholders to total equity holdings of the company (Lin, 2013).

8. **Corporate governance score:** This is derived based on the provisions of corporate governance framework in each of the respective countries (Researcher's innovation, 2023).
9. **Firm age:** measured with the number of years from the year of listing in the NGX (Aburime, 2008).

4. Presentation and Discussion of Multivariate Results

4.1. Panel Regressions

Table 1: 2SLS and System GMM Regression Result

<i>Variable</i>	Apriori Sign	2SLS	GMM
	FV		
CGS	+/-	32.380 (1.944) {0.054}	9.324 (1.105) {0.272}
BDS	+/-	-1.812 (-3.867) {0.000}	-0.290 (-0.595) {0.553}
BND	+/-	-72.013 (-4.957) {0.000}	-4.641 (-0.467) {0.642}
BFEXP	+	-8.950 (-0.421) {0.675}	21.405 (2.148) {0.035}
MOWN	-	-0.411 (-5.278) {0.000}	0.017 (0.096) {0.924}

INSOWN	-	-0.355 (-5.245) {0.000}	0.029 (0.182) {0.856}
FOWN	+	0.238 (4.079) {0.000}	0.172 (0.972) {0.334}
FA	+	-0.345 (-3.053) {0.003}	
			<i>Model Parameters</i>
R		0.332	-
R ²		0.276	-
F-statistic		18.240	-
Prob(F-statistic)		0.000	-
J-statistic		-	18.135
J-stat. prob		0.287	0.256
Wald-test, F-state		20.633 (2, 95)	4.026 (2, 84)
Wald-test, F-prob.		0.000	0.021
Instrument Rank		19	22
<i>Arellano-Bond Serial Correlation Test</i>			
AR(1)-p-value		-	0.619
AR(2)-p-value		-	0.000

T-Statistic (); p-value { }; ***, ** & * sig @ 5%

Source: Researcher's compilation (2023)

Table 1 shows the regression result using both the 2SLS and the GMM for corporate governance impacting firm value. For the 2SLS, the summary statistics show that $R = 0.332$ which suggests that the explanatory variables jointly explain about 33.2% of the systematic variation in firm value with an adjusted value (R^2) of 27.6%. The F-statistical probability value of 0.000 indicates that there is a significant linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables at 5%, this is also confirmed by the Wald test probability value of 0.000 which is significant even at 1%. The J-statistical probability value of 0.287 indicates that the over identification restrictions of the instrument is valid while the instrument rank is 19. Commenting on the performance of the corporate governance variables, the CGS which is a proxy for multi dimensional approach (board composition, assurance and auditing, ownership structure and relationship with shareholders, business conduct and ethics, sustainability issues and transparency) of corporate governance practices exhibits positive (32.380) impact on firm value and this is statistically significant at 5% ($p=0.05$). The result suggests that an increase in corporate governance practices will increase firm value by 32.38 units and this is significant.

For the GMM, the summary statistics show that the J-statistic probability value of 0.256 indicates that the over identification restrictions of the instrument is valid. Wald test probability value of 0.000 which is significant even at 1% indicates that there is a significant linear relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. The AR (1) test give p-values of 0.619 which indicates that the residuals in first differences are not correlated, while the AR (2) test gives p-value of 0.000 is below 0.05, which means indicates that the explanatory variables and the error term are endogenously related, this tends to undermine the regression estimates, hence the result may not be suitable for inferences, consequently policy implication. However, commenting on the performance of the corporate governance variables, the CGS exhibits positive (9.324) impact on firm value, although this is statistically insignificant at 5% ($p= 0.272$). The result suggests that an increase in corporate governance practices will increase firm value by 9.324 units, however caution should be exercised because it didn't pass the test of significance.

Table 2: 2SLS and System GMM Regression Result

<i>Variable</i>	Apriori Sign	2SLS	GMM
	CGS		
FV	+/-	0.009 (2.743) {0.007}	0.007 (1.225) {0.224}
BDS	+/-	0.022 (2.795) {0.006}	0.003 (0.292) {0.771}
BND	+/-	0.417 (1.368) {0.175}	-0.270 (-1.144) {0.256}
BFEXP	+	0.567 (2.039) {0.044}	0.100 (0.371) {0.712}
MOWN	-	0.005 (3.778) {0.000}	0.004 (1.028) {0.307}
INSOWN	-	0.004 (2.902) {0.005}	0.010 (3.125) {0.002}
FOWN	+	-0.002 (-2.559) {0.012}	0.003 (0.570) {0.570}

FA	+	0.003 (1.909) {0.059}	
			<i>Model Parameters</i>
R		0.284	-
R ²		0.224	-
F-statistic		8.727	-
Prob(F-statistic)		0.000	-
J-statistic		-	22.276
J-stat. prob		0.114	0.101
Wald-test, F-state		30756.88 (2, 95)	3546.457 (2, 84)
Wald-test, F-prob.		0.000	0.000
Instrument Rank		16	22
<i>Arellano-Bond Serial Correlation Test</i>			
AR(1)-p-value		-	0.867
AR(2)-p-value		-	0.024

T-Statistic (); p-value { }; ***, ** & * sig @ 5%

Source: Researcher's compilation (2023)

Table 2 shows the regression result using both the 2SLS and the GMM for firm value impacting corporate governance. For the 2SLS, the summary statistics show that R= 0.284 which suggests that the explanatory variables jointly explain about 28.4% of the systematic variation in firm value with an adjusted value (R²) of 22.4%. The F-statistic probability value of 0.000 indicates that there is a significant linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables at 5%, this is also confirmed by the Wald test probability value of 0.000 which is significant even at 1%. The J-statistic probability value of 0.114 indicates that the over identification restrictions is valid while the instrument rank is 16. Commenting on the performance of the explanatory variables, FV exhibits positive (0.009) impact on corporate governance and this is statistically significant at 5% (p= 0.007). The

result suggests that an increase in firm value will increase corporate governance practices by 0.009 units and this is significant. FA exhibits positive (0.003) impact on corporate governance, although this is statistically insignificant at 5% ($p=0.060$).

For the GMM, the summary statistics show that the J-statistic probability value of 0.101 indicates that the over identification restrictions of the instrument is valid. Wald test probability value of 0.000 which is significant even at 1% indicates that there is a significant linear relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. The AR(1) test give p-values of 0.867 which indicates that the residuals in first differences are not correlated, while the AR(2) test gives p-value of 0.024 is below 0.05, which means indicates that the explanatory variables and the error term are endogenously related, this tends to undermine the regression estimates, hence the result may not be suitable for inferences, consequently policy implication. However, commenting on the performance of the explanatory variables, FV exhibits positive (0.007) impact on corporate governance, although this is statistically insignificant at 5% ($p=0.224$). The result suggests that an increase in firm value will increase corporate governance by 0.007 units, however caution should be exercised because it didn't pass the test of significance.

4.2 Test of Hypotheses and Discussion of Findings

The test of hypotheses is done using the 2SLS in tables 4 and 5. Giving that the GMM result didn't pass the AR (2) which is a fundamental requirement for GMM estimation, the estimates may not be relied upon. Therefore, this study proceed to test the hypotheses using the 2SLS.

H_{01} : There is no significant causal relationship between corporate governance and market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

The estimation result revealed that CGS exhibits a positive and significant impact (32.380, $p=0.05$) at 5% on firm value. The result suggests that an increase in corporate governance practices will increase firm value by 32.38 units and this is significant. Conversely, the estimation result also revealed that FV exhibits a positive significant impact (0.009, $p=0.007$) at 5% on corporate governance. The result suggests that an increase in firm value will increase corporate governance practices by 0.009 units and this is significant. The foregoing suggests that the relationship between corporate governance and firm value is casual. Therefore, the H_{01} that there is no significant causal relationship between corporate governance and market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange is rejected. This finding is in tandem with theoretical expectation that a firm's value can affect its corporate governance

practices drive vice versa. Corporate governance impacting firm value is consistent with the studies of: Chhaochharia and Laeven (2009) using the ISS database found that firms that voluntarily adopt a more rigorous corporate governance structure are rewarded with a higher firm value; Aggarwal and Williamson (2006) and Brown and Caylor (2006) using the ISS database to construct governance indices for U.S. firms found a positive relationship between corporate governance and firm value; Gompers et al. (2003) using Investor Responsibility Research Center (IRRC) data found that firms with fewer shareholder rights have lower firm valuations and lower stock returns; and Brown and Caylor (2005) using a far more extensive database than the IRRC database show that their new Gov.-Score increases in firm value. The positive relationship between corporate governance and firm value is in tandem with theoretical expectation that a well governed firm will improve its market value. On the other hand, Demsetz and Lehn (1985) posit that firms may endogenously select different governance practices; therefore, firms may actually play dual roles – both passive and active – in their governance practices. Thus, not only are firm values affected by governance practices, but they will also actively improve their governance practices to achieve higher valuation (Bhagat & Bolton, 2008).

H₀₂: Board independence has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.

The estimation result revealed that BND exhibits inverse (-72.013) impact on firm value and this is statistically significant at 5% ($p=0.000$). The result suggests that an increase in BND will reduce firm value by 72.013 units and this is significant. Therefore, the H_{02} that *board independence has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange is rejected*. The findings is in tandem with Dung (2011) who found that the number of independent directors are significant impact on firm value.

H₀₃: Board size has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange

The estimation result revealed that BDS exhibits inverse (-1.812) impact on firm value and this is statistically significant at 5% ($p=0.000$). The result suggests that an increase in BDS will reduce firm value by 1.812 units and this is significant. Therefore, the H_{03} that *board size has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange is rejected*. The findings is in tandem with Yermack (1996) found an inverse relation between board size and Tobin's Q.

H₀₄: Board financial expertise has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange

BFEXP exhibits inverse (-8.950) impact on firm value, however statistically insignificant at 5% ($p= 0.675$). The result suggests that an increase in BFEXP will reduce firm value by 8.950 units, although insignificant. Therefore, the H_{04} that *board financial expertise has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange is accepted.*

H₀₅: Managerial ownership has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange

MOWN exhibits inverse (-0.411) impact on firm value and statistically significant at 5% ($p= 0.000$). The result suggests that an increase in MOWN will reduce firm value by 0.411 units and it is significant. Therefore, the H_{05} that *managerial ownership has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange is rejected.* The inverse relationship is not unlikely. Greater managerial ownership benefits share-holders because it increases managers' incentives to increase firm value. But when managerial ownership becomes too large, it enables managers to entrench themselves, so that firm value falls as managerial ownership increases beyond a certain point. Because of these countervailing forces, the relation between firm value and managerial ownership is not monotonic, and there is an optimal level of ownership.

H₀₆: Institutional ownership has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange

INSOWN exhibits inverse (-0.355) impact on firm value and statistically significant at 5% ($p= 0.000$). The result suggests that an increase in INSOWN will reduce firm value by 0.355 units and it is significant. Therefore, the H_{06} that *institutional ownership has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange is rejected.* The findings is in tandem with the study of Feng-Li Lin (2010) who found that institutional ownership impact firm value, however with a threshold effect.

H₀₇: Foreign ownership has no significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange

FOWN exhibits positive (0.238) impact on firm value and statistically significant at 5% ($p= 0.000$). The result suggests that an increase in FOWN will increase firm value by 0.238 units and it is significant. Therefore, the H_{07} that *foreign ownership has no*

significant relationship with market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange is rejected. This finding is consistent with Reeb et al (2001) who posits that the higher in foreign funding, the lower cost of debt owned by firm may increase firm value.

5. Conclusion

The market value of a firm, reflected through the stock market price is an important concept for investors because it shows how well the market perceives the company. The stock market price reflects the potentials of the company in the future or the overall investor's assessment of its own capital owned by a particular company. This suggests that a high share price indicates shareholders' prosperity vice versa. Therefore, understanding the determinants of a firm's market value is an important question that has attracted substantial research in accounting and other allied disciplines such as finance. The separation of ownership from control, and the potential agency conflicts that this separation engenders could lead to firm value being eroded. Managers could engage in self-seeking tendencies and this tends to undermine the value of the firm. Therefore, corporate governance deals with mechanisms by which stakeholders of a corporation exercise control over corporate insiders and management such that their interests are protected. Although the relationship between firm value and corporate governance has been examined, however, it remains unclear as to whether this relationship is causal, i.e. the whether the relationship is bidirectional, specifically from an emerging economy such as Nigeria. Premised on the foregoing, the study hypothesized that H_{01} : *there is no significant causal relationship between corporate governance and market value of firms listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange.* Employing both the 2SLS and GMM estimation techniques, the causal link between firm value and corporate governance was examined. Due to the unreliability of the GMM estimates, the study relied on the 2SLS for inferences and the result showed that there exist a causal link between both variables, i.e. both are endogenously determined and this is also in tandem with theoretical expectation. The study concludes that corporate governance impact firm value vice versa. The study made the following recommendations: (i) the study found the existence of bi-directional causal link between corporate governance and firm value. The positive and significant relationship is in tandem with theoretical expectation that a well governed firm will improve its market value. Therefore, the study recommends that firms should actively improve their governance practices in order to achieve higher valuation; (ii) board size was found to have a significant impact on firm value. Though there is yet no consensus regarding what constitutes an optimal board size, there is the need to ensure that the present board size is

efficient in improving corporate monitoring and then financial reporting quality. In this regard, the composition of the board should be examined with a view of including individuals with the needed competence and reputation to improve reporting credibility; (iii) board independence was found to have a significant impact on firm value. Therefore, the study recommends that a substantial proportion of corporate board should be non-executive directors with integrity and a reputation for transparency. In addition, such individuals should be involved in sensitive responsibilities that relate to improving reporting credibility; (iv) board financial expertise was found to have insignificant impact on firm value. This may suggest that board financial literacy may not be a sufficient condition for firm value. However, the study recommends that the need for more financial literacy board members and that the process of financial skill development is a continuous one and as such with advances in the techniques of managerial manipulation, board members need to update and upgrade their financial literacy levels especially incorporating forensic techniques and machine learning abilities which is the new approach for fraud detection; (v) managerial ownership was found to have a significant impact on firm value which suggests that substantial presence of managerial equity do impact firm value. However, there is the need for the board to be careful of the possibility of managerial entrenchment hypothesis which states that insider ownership can become ineffective in aligning insiders to take value-maximizing decisions. Therefore, there is need to look out for an optimal level of managerial ownership that will not be detrimental to the company; (vi) institutional ownership was found to have a significant impact on firm value. The study recommends more institutional presence but not in a passive mode but actively involved in ensuring corporate transparency; and (vii) foreign ownership was found to have a significant impact on firm value. However, the study recommends the presence of foreign ownership as it may foreign owners could more active in monitoring corporate activity giving their diverse exposure.

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